

ISic1316

I.Sicily inscription 1316

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Assumed to be from Catania, first attested in the collection of the Benedettini by Torremuzza

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di Catania, inventory 298

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 22.5 cm

Width 23.5 cm

Depth 1-6 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Μ(άρκος) Βιψάνιος Ζώ

2. σιμος ζήσα

3. ς καλῶς ἔτη · λε

4. χαῖ·ρε

5. παροδεῖτα

Apparatus

Text of Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

Markos Bipsanios Zosimos (Marcus Vipsanios), having lived well for 35 years.

Farewell passerby.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492921

EDCS 39101686

PHI 140809

PHI 316243

Bibliography

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